

InsigH₂t

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Scientific insights into H₂ combustion under elevated pressure conditions

Turbulent premixed hydrogen/air flame at gas turbine conditions (Image courtesy of RWTH Aachen)

Concept

InsigH₂t will acquire the fundamental scientific understanding of the effect of pressure on the turbulent burning rate, thermoacoustic response, and emissions performance of lean premixed hydrogen flames under gas turbine relevant conditions.

4 years (Jan 25 – Dec 28)

Budget €6.2M

Innovation

Fostering sustainable innovation and improving EU competitiveness

Reduce dependency on fossil fuels

Provide opportunities to utilise existing infrastructure

Transfer to the wider technical and scientific community

Main impacts

Advancing fundamental knowledge

Improving gas turbines technology

Decarbonising electric power sector and industrial processes

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